

PEDAGOGICAL POSSIBILITIES OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' SELF-STUDY LEARNING COMPETENCES IN CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM

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Abstract. *Self-study learning activity is based on the need to acquire knowledge that is important for the student. The pedagogical possibilities of self-study learning are determined by the independent mastery of cognitive activity methods. The development of self-study (Independent) learning competencies of the student, which serve to acquire independent knowledge, is of great importance. The article describes the pedagogical possibilities of developing students' self-study learning competencies in the credit-module system.*

Keywords: *Self-study (Independent) learning, competence, students, ensuring independence, increasing personal cognitive activity, ensuring social integration, directing teaching methods towards self-study learning activities, quality control.*

Improving the methodology for developing students' self-study (Independent) learning competencies in the credit-module system creates the following pedagogical opportunities:

1. *Ensuring independence.* The credit-module system allows students to be independent in choosing their own educational path, planning their lessons and studying. This, in turn, develops students' independent thinking skills.

In the literature, three levels of mastery of educational material are distinguished, and understanding through mastery is understood not only as the perception and understanding of information, but also as the ability to use the acquired knowledge as a means of solving new problems:

- characterized by "remembering and subsequently repeating the material being studied" (helps in accumulating knowledge, factual information);
- applying knowledge in practice (the ability to use knowledge, etc.);
- applying knowledge in non-traditional conditions (consists of a creative approach to solving problems, independent assessment of phenomena, facts, events, transformation of knowledge, use of their combination).

It should be noted that ensuring student independence in the educational process requires certain conditions. The credit-module system reflects these conditions.

2. *Increasing personal cognitive activity.* An important aspect of self-study (Independent) learning of students of higher educational institutions operating on the basis of the credit-module system is the activity of students during the process of acquiring knowledge.

Active learning is one of the foundations of independent cognitive activity.

The effectiveness of a student's activity serving self-study learning depends on their personal characteristics, the possession of the necessary skills and qualifications, and most importantly, cognitive activity. The cognitive activity of students in the process of self-study learning is characterized by the following stages:

- identifying a problem in objective reality;
- selecting and developing a solution aimed at a specific goal;

selecting methods for completing tasks;
identifying sources of self-study (Independent) learning;
working with information sources;
analyzing and summarizing new knowledge obtained in relation to the problem being solved;
self-control.

Therefore, in the credit-module system, self-study (Independent) learning of students cannot be achieved without cognitive activity; in this process, it is necessary to study personal characteristics and cognitive activity that serve to acquire knowledge.

3. *Ensuring social integration.* Students' competence in self-study (Independent) learning is also related to social integration. Because students need to find their place in the community and society, strengthen social ties.

Ensuring social integration requires considering issues of socialization in education.

Researchers suggest not contrasting social experience and educational (learning) experience, but combining them in teaching students. Knowledge should not be contrasted with skills and abilities consisting of actions with certain characteristics, but should be considered as their component. Knowledge cannot be acquired or stored outside the activity of the learner [6].

Students' self-study (Independent) learning is manifested in their assessment and understanding of the social significance of phenomena.

In higher educational institutions operating on the basis of the credit-module system, the experience of social activity is of great importance in stimulating students' self-study (Independent) learning. In this case, self-study (Independent) learning activities are socialized, which ensures the orientation of students to professional activities based on self-study learning.

The development of students' self-study learning competencies allows them to socially evaluate perceived objects or phenomena.

4. *Orient teaching methods towards self-study learning activities.* In order to stimulate students' self-study learning in the credit-module system, it is necessary to use effective teaching methods. The orientation of teaching methods to self-study learning activities reflects new approaches to choosing the most rational way to solve a professional problem, using information processing methods in a creative approach to the task.

According to researchers, in order to master general methods of learning, students need to “separate these methods and methods from the concepts and phenomena they use in the learning process, and use them as subjects of independent study” [8].

I.A.Zimnyaya identified the conditions for the formation of interest in learning: the opportunity to think freely and show initiative in teaching (the use of active methods of education); the creation of a problem situation (the difficulties created should be possible for the student); a reasonable variety of the content and methods of educational work; explains the emotional coloring of the presentation of the material [2].

Teaching methods focused on self-study learning activities should be considered as interconnected components. Teaching methods focused on self-study (Independent) learning activities help students develop new ways of processing knowledge, expand the possibilities for the student to apply known teaching methods in practice.

With the help of teaching methods focused on self-study learning activities, the student masters the main methods of self-study learning activities, can choose and use the necessary

methods to solve the problem, and independently draw up his own action plan based on certain knowledge.

The functions of teaching methods aimed at self-study learning activities are:
to master new methods of self-study (Independent) learning activities;
to help apply the acquired knowledge;
to enable students to master new methods of cognition in the process of learning;
to form an interest in the development of self-study (Independent) learning activities;
to develop the ability to choose the most rational way to solve a professional problem;
to master creative approaches to solving professional problems.

Teaching methods aimed at self-study learning activities are based on mastering methods and means of self-study (Independent) learning.

5. *Quality control.* Effective mechanisms are required to assess the effectiveness of students in the process of self-study learning. This, in turn, will help improve the quality of education.

An important aspect that determines the development of students' self-study (Independent) learning competencies in the credit-module system is the clarity and realism of the goal of self-study (Independent) learning activities by students, the presence of constant control.

Researchers, analyzing the process of developing self-study learning activities in students in higher education institutions operating on the basis of the credit-module system, distinguish the following aspects of the organization of the process (structure, motivational sphere, presentation of material, beginning and end of the lesson): general learning abilities of students (organization of self-study learning, self-assessment, improvement of one's knowledge and skills, self-education, self-control), formation of methods of mental activity by the teacher (comparison, generalization, understanding, discussion, reasoning, imagination), student activity (imagination, reproduction of acquired knowledge, independent work, use of knowledge, research, creativity), personal approach of the teacher (positive motivation, formation of the concept of "self", individual approach, individual approach) [4].

In the credit-module system, it is possible to conditionally divide the process of controlling the development of students' self-study learning competencies into two parts: external and internal control.

In this case, internal control is more important and more important than external control.

External control. The formation of the need for self-study learning is of great importance for students to become mature, competent, and qualified specialists in their field. Control in self-study learning is one of the main factors in self-study learning. In self-study learning, first of all, it is necessary to form control mechanisms along with the need for students to work independently, to engage in free, creative activities.

The main task of developing students' self-study learning competencies in the credit-module system is to replace external control and assessment with self-management and self-control.

This process includes determining the purpose of the activity; developing an action plan to achieve the goal; determining the form, method and time of self-control [7].

Internal control. Self-control skills are formed on the basis of students' choice of rational methods of self-study (Independent) learning activities.

Self-study learning activities are carried out on the basis of self-management, in particular,

self-control.

Self-control in the development of students' self-study (Independent) learning competencies is associated with will.

Will is the ability of a person to consciously regulate his actions and activities that require overcoming internal and external difficulties, to consciously control and actively manage his activities, to overcome obstacles and consciously subordinate them to a set goal [3], the perceptual side, its active and regulatory principle, a mechanism designed to create action and maintain it when necessary [5].

Psychologists emphasize that there are certain conditions and obstacles to the control of human will. The diversity of such obstacles can be expressed in the following three realities, which, when a person lacks sufficient motivation, he feels the need for some kind of motivating force to act: motives, goals and the types of activities necessary to achieve these goals, internal and external activities, and the ability to control mental processes [5].

A person can control his will and develop his behavior in various ways. For example, this can be achieved by transforming involuntary mental processes into voluntary processes, controlling his actions and activities, and developing emotional and volitional qualities. As a result of volitional self-control, a person sets more promising goals for himself, requiring more significant volitional aspirations in the long term [1].

Summarizing the research, it should be said that the research considers such functions of self-study learning as self-awareness and self-control.

The underdevelopment of students' self-study (Independent) learning competencies is also reflected in the low level of self-control and low procedural indicators.

In conclusion, it can be said that the credit-module system requires the development of clear strategies for identifying socio-professional problems in the development of students' self-study learning competencies and ways to solve them.

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